

DIAGNOSTIC APPROCH ON ALZHEIMER'S DISEASE

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ABSTRACT

Alzheimer's disease is the most common type of dementia, characterized by a progressive decline in cognitive function, particularly memory and impacting daily life. It is a neurodegenerative disorder involving the abnormal build-up of proteins in the brain forming plaques. These protein aggregates and disrupt normal brain cell function leading to neuron damage. It is an undertreated and under-recognized disease that is becoming a major public health problem. The last decade has witnessed a steadily increasing effort directed at discovering the aetiology of the disease and developing pharmacological treatment. This disease starts after the age of 55-60 but in down syndrome patients it starts earlier at the age of 40-50. Some of the chemicals used as inducing agents are scopolamine, colchicine, Okadaic acid, Trimethyl tin and some of the metal ions are used in animal models. Alzheimer's disease is similar

to that of coronary heart disease or ischemic. **Background:** - It was first described in 1906 by Dr. Alois Alzheimer, after studying a patient named Auguste D, who exhibited symptoms like memory loss and language problem.

KEYWORD: Alzheimer's disease, cognitive impairment, loss of memory, tau protein, beta amyloid, oxidative stress.

1. INTRODUCTION

1.1 What are ALZHEIMER'S disease

Alzheimer's disease is a progressive condition that gradually damages the brain, leading to the loss of memory, thinking abilities, and, over time, even basic daily functioning. It also causes noticeable shifts in mood, behavior, and personality.^[1]

More than 6 million Americans, many of them age 65 and older, are estimated to have Alzheimer's disease. That's more individuals living with Alzheimer's disease than the population of a large American city. Many more people experience Alzheimer's in their lives as family members and friends of those with the disease.^[2]

The end of neuron called synapses through these synapses information flows into other neuron with help of tiny bursts carrying chemicals that are released by one end of the neuron (presynaptic) in synaptic cleft and detected by another neuron (postsynaptic). Brain contains 150 billion of neurons which will allow the signals to travel more rapidly to the brain neuronal circuits these results in creating the more cellular basis such as thoughts, thinking, sensation, movements, skills, and memories etc.^[8,9]

1.2 Clinical Features

The commonest presentation of AD is of an elderly individual with insidious, progressive problems centred on episodic memory. At this stage, the patient may fulfil criteria for amnesic mild cognitive impairment (MCI). Topographical difficulties subsequently commonly emerge, alongside difficulties with multi-tasking, and loss of confidence. As the condition progresses, cognitive difficulties become more profound and widespread so as to interfere with activities of daily living; at this stage a patient can be diagnosed with AD dementia. Increasing dependence is the rule, and later in the disease behavioural change, impaired mobility, hallucinations and seizures may emerge. Death is on average 8.5 years from presentation.^[13]

Fig. No. 01: Health Brain and Shrunken Brain in Alzheimer's Condition.

1.3 HISTORY

Alzheimer's disease was first identified by German psychiatrist and neuropathologist Alois Alzheimer in the early 20th century.

1901

Alois Alzheimer begins studying Auguste Deter, who is experiencing symptoms of what would later be recognized as Alzheimer's disease.^[23]

1906

At a conference in Tübingen, Alzheimer presents his findings on Auguste Deter, including the pathological characteristics of the disease: amyloid plaques and neurofibrillary tangles.

1910

Emil Kraepelin officially names the condition "Alzheimer's disease" in the 8th edition of his textbook, "Clinical Psychiatry".

Early to mid-20th century

Alzheimer's disease is initially considered a rare form of presenile dementia, affecting individuals younger than 65.

Later 20th century

Research progresses, and scientists begin to understand the role of amyloid plaques and neurofibrillary tangles in the disease.

Late 20th and early 21st century

Advances in neuroimaging techniques (like PET scans) and genetic research help refine diagnostic criteria and reveal potential risk factors for Alzheimer's disease.^[24]

2. PATHOPHYSIOLOGY

Alzheimer's disease is a neurodegenerative and prominent protein conformational disease (PCD)^[25,26] caused by polymerization of abnormal neuronal proteins^[27] in a misfolded pattern due to the genetic mutation, ageing, abnormal neuronal function, and external factors etc.^[28]

The Pathophysiology of AD is unclear. But many of researchers reported that Alzheimer's disease is due to the various hypotheses as follows.^[29,30]

- a. B amyloid hypothesis
- b. Tau hypothesis
- c. Cholinergic hypothesis
- d. Oxidative stress hypothesis
- f. Metal ion hypothesis

a. Amyloid Hypothesis

This hypothesis suggests that the accumulation of A β plaques is the primary trigger for AD, leading to the formation of tangles and subsequent neurodegeneration. The pathology of Alzheimer's disease (AD) involves the loss of neuronal cells. Which is mainly starts in the hippocampus of brain and followed by amygdala, entorhinal cortex and also in association with frontal, temporal, parietal. It also involved in the sub cortical nucleus are serotonergic dorsal raphe, nor-adrenergic locus coeruleus and also cholinergic basal nucleus.^[31]

Fig. No. 02: Beta amyloid Hypothesis.

b. Tau Hypothesis

This hypothesis proposes that abnormal tau protein aggregation is the central event in AD pathogenesis, leading to synaptic dysfunction and neuronal death. These are insoluble twisted fibres of a protein called Tau. Tau helps stabilize microtubules which are essential for transporting the nutrients and other molecules within neurons.^[32]

i. Normal Tau

Normally, the tau protein helps stabilize microtubules, which are essential for maintaining cell structure and transporting nutrients and molecules within neurons.

ii. Hyperphosphorylation

In Alzheimer's, tau becomes abnormally hyperphosphorylated, meaning it has too many phosphate groups attached.

iii. Microtubule Disassembly

Hyperphosphorylated tau detaches from microtubules, causing them to disassemble and the microtubules to destabilize.

iv. Tangle Formation

The detached tau protein then aggregates into insoluble filaments that form neurofibrillary tangles inside the neurons.

v. Cellular Dysfunction and Death

The accumulation of tangles and loss of microtubule function impairs intracellular transport and synaptic function, eventually leading to nerve cell death and contributing to the cognitive decline seen in AD.^[33]

Fig. No. 03: Tau Hypothesis.

c. Cholinergic hypothesis

Cholinergic hypothesis involves the loss of the cholinergic neurons in the hippocampus of the brain. Loss of cholinergic neurons leads to depletion of acetylcholine neurotransmitter in the brain of AD patients. Cholinergic hypothesis is due to A β plaques, hyperphosphorylation of tau protein, and acetylcholinesterase (AChE) enzyme. Acetylcholinesterase (AChE) is an important enzyme involved in the cleavage of acetylcholine into acetate and choline.^[34] Amount of acetylcholinesterase in brain can be calculated by Ell man's method by using acetylthiocholine as artificial substrate.^[35] Acetylcholinesterase inhibitors (AChEIs) are the medications inhibit the action of acetylcholinesterase on acetylcholine neurotransmitter and enhance the action of acetylcholine in postsynaptic membrane. Acetylcholinesterase inhibitors (AChEIs) are the most important medication used in the treatment of AD. As the AD starts to progress the cholinergic neurons will also start to deplete with nicotinic receptors in hippocampus and cortex of the brain. But nicotinic receptors in the presynaptic membranes will control release of acetylcholine.^[36]

Fig. No. 05: Diagrammatic representation of Cholinergic Hypothesis.

d. Oxidative stress hypothesis

Oxidative stress defines as the “loss of cell equilibrium enhanced by the imbalance between production of prooxidant (ROS) and activity of antioxidants molecules as defence system”.

During normal physiological conditions prooxidants are at lower concentration in tissue involved in signalling molecules for cell proliferation, cell growth, redox homeostasis, as well as cellular signal transduction.^[37]

Many of researcher reported that AD is associated with lower antioxidant defence and higher level of oxidative stress. It may be the free radicals generated will alter the metabolism of metal in brain leads to the aggregation of amyloid β causes toxicity.^[38]

Fig. No. 06: Diagrammatic representation of Oxidative stress Hypothesis.

e. Metal ion hypothesis

Metal ions are one of the most important for normal neuronal function. Transport and circulation of metals in the brain is mainly regulated by blood brain barrier (BBB). Distraction of the normal physiology of metal homeostasis in brain has an important role in pathogenesis of Alzheimer's disease.^[42]

The important parts of the brain are hippocampus, amygdale, and CSF were found to contain various metal ions such as iron, zinc, copper, cadmium, and chromium and also these areas of brain also found to be containing both senile plaques, neurofibrillary tangles (NFT).^[43,44,45]

The intrinsically mammalian brain may contain much higher level of zinc, copper, and iron than that of other tissue. Because of brain contain various enzymes dependent on metals for its activation and metal dependent metabolic process.^[46] Metals involved in the production of free radicals by the Fenton like reaction they also interact with various biomolecules like A β , AchE, and Ach in AD.^[47]

Iron: It has been reported that deficiency of Fe²⁺ may leads to the abnormal neuronal function and cognitive impairment. So, it is important for normal healthy brain. But sometimes it is toxic to the tissues of brain by damaging the tissues of brain by trauma, stroke. It was reported that AD brains have higher Fe²⁺ than that of normal brain and get accumulate in the regions of hippocampus and cortex. These regions are important for

thought and memory. Fe²⁺ interact with plaques, tangles, lesions result in loss of memory, thought and cognitive impairment.^[48]

Copper: Copper (Cu²⁺) is divalent metal cation found in various enzymes like SOD, Cytochrome-C oxidase, tyrosinase, ceruloplasmin etc. It is essential for normal biochemical pathways in non-neuronal and neuronal cells. Copper is released from neurons by activation of NMDA receptors; it regulates the activation of neuronal cells and entry of Ca²⁺ into cells.^[49] astrocytes are subtype of microglia cells that has various copper containing enzymes. Higher the amount of copper containing astrocytes binding to A β results in the damage to the brain tissue due to the production of free radicals by Fenton like reaction results in oxidative stress and damage to brain cells.^[50]

Zinc: Zinc (Zn²⁺) it is a divalent metal ion found highest in neocortex of the brain. Zinc is a neurotoxin should be regulated during the deficiency and excess of zinc. It also has neuromodulatory property and inhibiting of NMDA excitatory receptors.^[51,52] Many studies reported that as the level of zinc increases the deposition of A β also increases and also reported that there is elevated level of zinc in the brains of the patient suffered with AD.^[53]

Chromium: Chromium (Cr³⁺) is a trivalent metal ion very important for the metabolism of carbohydrates. Studies reported that insulin signalling transduction system requires a chromium (Cr³⁺) and zinc (Zn²⁺) and are essential for normal insulin sensitivity.^[54]

Cadmium: Cadmium (Cd²⁺) it is a divalent metal cation which is non-essential and it has long biological half life hence it is classified as carcinogen. Cadmium produces the toxic effects because of accumulation of large quantity of metal ion in the brain tissue results in induced oxidative damage to the brain cells. Many of studies reported that cadmium is also one of the etiological factors for neurodegenerative disease like Alzheimer's disease. Cadmium targets the cerebral cortical surface and induces cell apoptosis.^[55]

3. Experimental drugs to induce Alzheimer's disease in experimental animal

A) Colchicine: It is alkaloidal drug with molecular formula C₂₂H₂₅O₆ extracted from the plant of lily family which was used previously to treat arthritis.^[56] Colchicine is a neurotoxin interrupts and disintegrates the tubulin dimers of microtubules by binding to it leads to the loss of cholinergic neurons, decreases the acetylcholine neurotransmitter results in the impairment in the thinking, recognizing, memory loss.

Research studies reported that after the 2-3 weeks of administration of colchicine shows the abnormal behavioural and changes in level of neurochemicals.^[58] Other studies also reported that ICV administration of colchicine's shows decreased the acetylcholine and glutathione in the brains of rats further leads to oxidative damage and cognitive impairment.^[59]

B) Scopolamine: It is muscarinic receptor blocker blocks the cholinergic receptors in the brain and inhibits action mediated by acetylcholine. It will induce cognitive impairment in the animal by the destruction of neurons in the hippocampus leads to the loss of memory and learning new things in experimental animal models.^[62] Administration of scopolamine by intraperitoneal route shows the dose dependent the impaired cognitive dysfunction, cholinergic dysfunction in experimental rats and it was also reported to cause oxidative stress.^[63] Study reported that scopolamine decreases the activity of choline acetyltransferase (important enzyme responsible for synthesis of acetylcholine) in hippocampus and cortex of brain.^[64]

C) Streptozosine: Streptozosine is an antibiotic used as anticancer agents. Streptozosine is obtained from strain of *Streptomyces chromogenes*'s soil bacteria. Many studies reported that administration of Streptozosine at a dose of 3mg/kg results in decreased the weight of whole brain, and cognitive impairment, and also progressively increased the level of A β and tau in the hippocampus of the brain.^[65] In addition, some studies demonstrated that STZ causes damage to the special areas of brain such as anterior hippocampus, axons, myelin of the fornix, and also periventricular structure important role in learning, memory storage.^[66]

It reduces the creatine phosphate level by interfering with activity of glycolytic enzyme in the brain. This will reduce the acetyl COA synthesis in the brain and impairs the transmission of cholinergic neurons in brain.^[69]

E) OKA: Studies reported Okadaic acid will reduce the phosphates activity in the brains of AD patients.^[76] IN addition to that OKA cause elevation level of Ca²⁺ and lack of memory it had relationship in the toxicity in neuron.^[77] Studies also reported that increased intracellular calcium causes the accumulation of A β , and hyperphosphorylated tau leads to the toxicity and death of neurons in the brain. OKA interferes with normal calcium signalling results in alter phosphorylation and dephosphorylation of protein balance in brain leads to the abnormal phosphorylation of tau protein in brain.^[78]

F) Alcohol: It was reported that ethanol treatment will cause loss of memory, cognitive impairment. Because of damage in the neurons of hippocampus, sensory motor system, disruption of cholinergic neuron signalling, and interferes with glutamatergic system and also enhance the GABAergic transmission in memory related special areas of brain.^[79] It was reported that cognitive defects and defects in memory has shown in neonatal model of ethanol due to the feeding of ethanol in experimental animals.^[80]

5. RISK FACTORS

Age

The single greatest risk factor for developing Alzheimer's disease is age, one of the non-modifiable risk factors. Most cases of Alzheimer's disease are seen in older adults, ages 65 years or above. Between the ages of 65 and 74, approximately 5 percent of people have Alzheimer's disease. For those over 85, the risk increases to 50 percent.^[85]

Genetics

In sporadic Alzheimer's disease, there is no appearance of a genetic pattern of inheritance. A connection has been found between a gene called Apolipoprotein E (ApoE) and the development of Alzheimer's disease. This gene is supposed to be responsible for the protein that carries cholesterol in the blood vessels. One form of the gene, ApoE4, has been shown to increase the chances of developing the disease to a greater extent. However, the ApoE2 form protects from the disease.^[86] In the cases occurring before age 65, a mutation of chromosomes can be responsible. This rare form of the disease is called Familial Alzheimer's disease and it affects less than 10 percent of Alzheimer's disease patients.^[87]

Coexisting Health Problems

The symptoms of depression may include:

- Insomnia
- Mood swings
- Less contact with the people around
- difficulty in concentrating

6. DIAGNOSIS

6.1 Detection Methods

- A. PET
- B. CT

C. MRI

A. PET

Positron emission tomography (PET) uses radiation signals to create a three-dimensional colour image of the human body.^[90] The patient is injected with a radiotracer, composed of a radioactive medicine bound to a naturally occurring chemical. For the study of the Alzheimer's disease chemical is usually glucose and is used widely. The energy from these positrons is detected by the PET scan, which converts the input to an image on the output screen. A PET scan has the capacity to detect changes in metabolism, blood flow, and cellular communication processes in the brain and other activities taking place inside the brain.^[91]

Fig. No. 7: PET Machine.

B. CT

A computed tomography (CT) scan takes a series of cross-sectional images of the body.^[92] With the help of a computer, the individual scans are integrated and incorporated into one detailed image. The CT scan provides the physician with information about the density of tissues in the body and in various parts of the brain. For improved clarity, a contrast dye may be injected to provide a distinction between similar tissues.^[93]

Fig. No. 8: CT Scan Machine.

C. MRI

Magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) techniques, first used in 1977, create two or three-dimensional images of the body that can be used to diagnose injury and illness. The essential component of the MRI system is the super conducting magnet, which produces a large and stable magnetic field.^[94]

These magnets allow for different parts of the body to be scanned. The human body is composed of billions of atoms. However, it is the hydrogen atoms that are altered by the magnetic field. Hydrogen atoms are each randomly spinning around an axis, but inside the magnetic field of the MRI, the molecules are lined up with the direction of the field. Half of the atoms point towards the patient's head, and half point toward the feet, cancelling each other out. A few atoms out of every million are not cancelled out. The machine then emits a radio frequency pulse specific to hydrogen, which causes these protons to spin in a different direction. When the spinning ceases, the protons release energy, which is interpreted by the system. Using a contrast dye, each type of issue responds differently and appears as a unique shade of grey when the image is created.^[90]

Fig. No. 9: MRI Machine.

7. TREATMENT

- 1) Drug Therapy
- 2) Cholinesterase inhibitors
- 3) Antidepressants & Antipsychotic

1) Drug Therapy

There are two types of medication used to treat Alzheimer's disease: acetylcholinesterase inhibitors and N-methyl D-aspartate antagonists. The two types work in different ways.

2) Cholinesterase inhibitors

In individuals with Alzheimer's disease, the brain contains reduced levels of a chemical called acetylcholine, which is responsible for transmitting messages between nerve cells. Cholinesterase inhibitors (CLs) work to enhance the availability of acetylcholine in synaptic transmission, thereby helping to manage memory, and galantamine are commonly used as first-line treatments for mild to moderate stages of Alzheimer's disease.^[96]

While donepezil and rivastigmine are both selective inhibitors, galantamine inhibits both Ach and butyrylcholinesterase. A meta-analysis collaborating 13 randomized, double-blind trials that were designed to evaluate the effectiveness and safety of Cis showed no improvement in ADL and behaviour. In addition, donepezil and rivastigmine showed no significant difference in their impact on cognitive functions, ADLs and behaviour. Overall, similar benefits were observed across all three drugs.^[97]

3) Antidepressants & Antipsychotic

Memantine helps manage these symptoms to some extent; however, as the disease progresses, the effectiveness of these medications gradually decreases. Depression is a frequent occurrence, particularly during the early and late stages of the condition. To address this, antidepressants such as selective serotonin reuptake inhibitors (SSRIs), tricyclic antidepressants, and combined serotonergic–noradrenergic agents may be prescribed.^[99]

Common antipsychotics used in Alzheimer's disease include olanzapine, quetiapine, and risperidone, which are administered to control psychosis and agitation. Nevertheless, their use remains controversial, as patients treated with antipsychotic medications have shown a more significant decline in cognitive function compared to those receiving a placebo.^[97]

8. OTHER TREATMENT

Ayurvedic treatments are regarded as supportive or complementary approaches for managing Alzheimer's disease rather than providing a complete cure. In Ayurveda, Alzheimer's is described as a progressive neurological condition (Manas Vyadhi) associated with an imbalance in Vata, dosha, which influences the nervous system and cognitive abilities. The treatment approach aims to restore this balance through the use of medicinal herbs, detoxification therapies, dietary modifications, and lifestyle changes to promote brain health, alleviate symptoms, and enhance overall quality of life.

Brahmi (*Bacopa monnieri*): Praised for enhancing memory, concentration, and protecting neurons.

Ashwagandha (*Withania somniferous*): An adaptogen that may reduce beta-amyloid plaque buildup, lower stress, and offer neuroprotective benefits.

Shankhpushpi (*Convolvulus pluricaulis*): Used to promote mental clarity and calm the nervous system.

Turmeric (*Curcuma longa*): Contains curcumin, which has powerful anti-inflammatory and antioxidant properties that can reduce inflammation.^[100]

9. CONCLUSION

In this article, Alzheimer's Disease and its clinical features are briefly discussed. Many of the herbal drugs and secondary metabolites also play a very important role in management of Alzheimer disease. Then after in pathophysiology we see the 5 hypothesis such as Beta amyloid hypothesis, Tau hypothesis, Cholinergic hypothesis, Oxidative stress hypothesis, Metal ion hypothesis this all are the causes of Alzheimer's disease. Some of the experimental drugs like OKA, TMT, STZ, colchicine, and scopolamine cause damage or loss of hippocampus neurons leads to AD. TMT is neurotoxin causes depression, anxiety, memory deficit, neuronal destruction, a Positron emission tomography, computed tomography and Magnetic resonance imaging are the techniques available for detection of Alzheimer's disease in patients induced degeneration of neuron in hippocampus of the brain. Cholinesterase inhibitors are the class of compounds used for treatment of Alzheimer disease. Current therapies for patients with Alzheimer's disease may ease symptoms by providing temporary improvement and reducing the rate of cognitive decline.

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